

Bernard Nkandu, Yvonne Chipongoma,

Lorraine Ledgerwood-Mundanya,

Vol 4:5 2024

Godfrey Mutara, Thamary Karonga & Elizabeth Ngun'u

Northrise University, Zambia

Corresponding author: ORCID Number: 0009-0006-0218-380XG; bernard.nkandu@northrise.net

ABSTRACT

Studying in overseas institutions presents students with exciting opportunities, however, with these opportunities comes challenges. Therefore, this research sought to explore the factors associated with challenges faced by internationally - trained health professionals in Copperbelt province, Zambia. The literature used comprised published articles from journals. The study utilized a Phenomenological descriptive qualitative research design and a convenience sampling method was used to select 26 participants from the Copperbelt province. Thematic analysis was used to present the experiences of the professionals while in foreign countries and after completion of the study. The results revealed various experiences relating to studying internationally, factors associated with the challenges faced and methods used to overcome the challenges. The study recommends that; the ministry of education and Zambian scholarship programs should introduce language programs prior to travel and ensure that when students are going abroad they are fully supported with financial assistance, if possible financial assistance be in American dollars to mitigate effects of kwacha depreciation. In addition, the Ministry of Health, Zambia should design a program for foreign trained health personnel to be integrated into the Zambian workforce without

difficulties. In conclusion the study identified various experiences that stood out from their time abroad. Many of the subthemes identified overlapped with common challenges that many international students face such as diet, weather, and language barriers. Although each of these subthemes were important experiences, more unique experiences revealed included challenges that stemmed from racial differences and integration into the Zambian workforce. Exploring these challenges and experiences led to the emphasis on the need for further research and exploration into these aspects of international experiences.

Keywords: *Internationally Trained, Health Professionals, Challenges, factors.*

INTRODUCTION

Problem Statement

While traveling overseas for studies comes with a lot of excitement, it is accompanied with anxious uncertainties about what students are likely to face or experience once they get to the foreign nation. Over the years there have been numerous studies regarding challenges faced by students studying in foreign nations. The commonly highlighted challenges include language barrier, financial challenges, cultural adjustments and loneliness as discussed in a study by Khanal and Gaulee (2019). As a result, some students are discontinued from their programs of study leading to deportation; others may resort to illegal activities such as drug trafficking and end up being jailed in a foreign country. Such students are prone to psychological distress and mental health conditions like depression because of failure to accomplish their goals. Identification of factors that are leading to these presented challenges is needed to help students circumvent failures in the future.

Significance of the Study

The findings of this research have useful implications for the government, the policy makers, and administrators of educational institutions of higher learning that seek to enroll international students, as well as prospective students. The government should be made aware of the factors associated with challenges faced by internationally trained health professionals, which will enable formulation of policies that will address these factors and ensure adequate support is provided. Additionally, the government will be recommended to invest in its citizens through the provision of scholarship programs for international study. The administrators of educational institutions will know the necessary measures to address the identified factors. The common factors leading to challenges encountered by international students have been highlighted, which provides information for prospective students and adequately prepares them to adjust and overcome the challenges when in the host country.

Research Questions

1. What experiences do internationally trained health professionals face while studying abroad?
2. Why are health professionals faced with challenges when they go overseas for studies?
3. How can challenges faced by internationally trained health professionals be addressed?

Purpose Statement

The purpose of the research was to explore the factors associated with challenges faced by internationally trained health professionals currently working in the Copperbelt Province in Zambia.

Scope, Limitation, and Delimitation of the Study

Several challenges were encountered while conducting the research. Recruitment of a sufficient number of participants was a challenge due to busy schedules of the study participants, the medical professionals. Despite this limitation, researchers were able to work around the time constraints of participants. In addition, the researchers had restricted time, being full-time lecturers, they had other duties like teaching and continuous assessment of students. Researchers worked together with their various schedules in order to overcome their time constraints.

This study was delimited methodologically by a qualitative component that involves in-depth interviews with a purposive sample of internationally trained health professionals currently working in Copperbelt Province in Zambia. The challenges faced by internationally trained health professionals was not the focus of this study as this topic has been frequently and exhaustively discussed in other studies. This study did not provide literature review on similar studies conducted locally as there is no available published literature on the factors associated with challenges faced by internationally trained health professionals.

METHODOLOGY

This study utilized qualitative research methods and a phenomenological research design so as to describe the factors leading to challenges faced by internationally trained Zambian health professionals. Creswell and Creswell (2018) states that, “phenomenological research design is a design of inquiry coming from philosophy and psychology in which the researcher studies the lived experiences of individuals about a phenomenon as described by participants” (p. 171). This study was conducted within the Copperbelt Province of Zambia, the setting was appropriate as it increased the chances of recruiting a sufficient sample. A convenience sampling method was used

to select twenty six (26) internationally-trained health professionals currently practicing within the Copperbelt Provinces in Zambia, who were interviewed using the Semi-structured face to face and phone interviews. Ethical approvals which were sought from Tropical Diseases Research Centre (TDRC) and the National Health Research Authority (NHRA).

FINDINGS

The themes and subthemes identified are presented within Table 1. Using a thematic analysis of participants’ experiences, the themes and subthemes were extracted in order to better understand the experiences, factors related to challenges, and measures to better handle identified challenges faced by Zambian medical professionals who received their education abroad.

Table 1

Summary of themes and subthemes.

Themes	Number of participants who discussed subject	Subthemes	Number of participants who discussed theme/ subtheme	Percentages of participants
Theme 1: Experiences	26	1.1. Foreign Languages	20	76.9%
		1.2. Diet	12	46.2%
		1.3. Weather	7	26.9%
		1.4. Racial Differences	17	65.4%
		1.5. Integration into Zambian Workforce	17	65.4%

Theme 2: Factors Associated with Challenges	26	2.1. Differences in Zambian and Foreign Curricula	11	42.3%
		2.2. Financial Restrictions	11	42.3%
		2.3. Inadequate Pre- Travel Knowledge	4	15.4%
		2.4. University Location	6	23.1%
		2.5. Inability to Learn Foreign Language Prior to Travel Abroad	3	11.5%
Theme 3: Measures Implemented to Overcome Challenges	26	3.1. Self-Motivation	5	19.2%
		3.2. Friend and Family Support	8	30.8%
		3.3. Mentorship and Support Programs	4	15.4%
		3.4. Avoidance Coping	7	26.9%

Demographic Data

There were 26 medical professionals who participated in the research interviews. Of the 26 interviews, 25 of the interviews took place via phone call. One interview took place in-person.

The demographic data is presented in Table 2. The majority (92%) of participants were medical doctors who studied in the countries of China (69%), followed by Russia (19%). One participant studies in the United Kingdom, one in Ukraine, and one in Cuba. Of the 26 participants, 24 studied medicine towards becoming medical doctors, one studied pharmacy, and one studies biomedical engineering.

Table 2*Demographic of interview participants.*

Category	Subcategory	Number of Participants	Percentage
Age	20-25	2	7.7%
	26-30	16	61.5%
	30-40	7	26.9%
	40+	1	3.8%
Gender	Male	10	38.5%
	Female	16	61.5%
Country in which participants studies abroad	China	18	69.2%
	Cuba	1	3.8%
	Russia	5	19.2%
	Ukraine	1	3.8%
	United Kingdom	1	3.8%
Living arrangements while abroad	Hostel (dormitory)	12	46.2%
	Apartment	2	7.7%
	Hostel and apartment at different times throughout stay abroad	11	42.3%
	Other (hotel)	1	3.8%
Profession/ study program	Medicine (medical doctor)	24	92.3%
	Pharmacy	1	3.8%
	Biomedical Engineering	1	3.8%
Length of study	Less than 1 year	1	3.8%
	1-3 years	1	3.8%
	4-6 years	16	61.5%
	More than 6 years	8	30.8%
Year of completion	2010-2015	5	19.2%
	2016-2020	11	42.3%
	2021-2024	10	38.5%

Theme 1: Experiences

Experiences are events or occurrences that leave an impression on someone. The aim of objective one of the research study was to explore the experiences of medical professionals who trained internationally. Many of the experiences recalled by participants revolved around the challenges they faced during their studies abroad along with the challenges faced when they returned to Zambia to join the workforce. The subthemes that were reoccurring within interviews included experiences related to foreign languages, diet, weather, racial differences, and integration into the Zambian workforce.

For those individuals who studied in China, most of the medical programs were taught in English. As participant #11 stated, “My program of study was taught in English, so that was an advantage as well.” The participants still found communicating outside of the classroom setting difficult, but the program of study itself did not have a significant language barrier. Differences in accents from professors and lecturers were a factor contributing to language barriers, though participants generally felt this was insignificant compared to learning Chinese. One of the participants who studied in China completed her program in Chinese because the policy of that university required it for students on scholarship. She noted that it was extremely challenging to master medical terminology in Chinese.

The participants who completed their medical studies in Russia and Ukraine found more challenges as their program of study was taught in the local language. They expressed the frustration of not only learning a new language to get around their new city or town, but also having to understand higher level medical terminology in order to be successful. Participant #10 stated that, “the first few months were a challenge because they don’t speak English and I did not know Russian. So it was a very big challenge to communicate, to get what you want, to move around.”

The challenge of settling into the new environment was compounded by the fact that locals only spoke in their native language and knew very little English. Another aspect that arose from learning medicine in a foreign language was the challenge in returning to Zambia and having to relearn terminology and phrasing in English in order to work.

The participant who studied in Cuba discussed similar challenges to other participants. Most foreign-speaking countries required a year of language courses and training to be completed prior to starting the program of study. Participants discussed that this was helpful, but not enough training to master the language. Participant #10 stated, “That’s very difficult, because everything that you know, that you’re supposed to know, you are supposed to do it in a different language. And you’re only given one year to learn the language.” As language is a pivotal element of communication, it is clear that the experiences surrounding issues of foreign language were significant to the participants.

Subtheme 1.2: Diet. When asked about experiences abroad, food was one aspect of experiences that stood out for participants. Many students who study abroad have an emotional need for food that is familiar to them. Traveling to a country with vastly different food cultures was brought up as something that stood out in their experiences. Getting used to a new food was brought forward by 12 (46%) of the 26 participants. One participant made mention of the fact that in Chinese culture animals such as dogs, cats, and rodents were used as meats and this not something they desired to integrate into their own diet; “diet, one needs to be careful and learn about the foods eaten in China” (Participant #15). Getting used to new, unfamiliar foods took time, just allowing time for foods to become more familiar was the reason cited for being able to overcome diet as a challenge. A longing for more familiar foods that Zambian students were accustomed to was also identified by participants.

5 participants (19%) felt that in order to adapt to the new food, time was the key factor. “I got used to the environment, got used to the food” (Participant #8). Participants felt they were able to overcome diet changes as a challenge with enough time and immersion in the culture. “Diet modification was another challenge. I had to get used to foods I was not familiar with” (Participant #13). “Getting used” to foods was one of the requirements the participants faced while studying internationally.

The longing for familiar foods can be an emotional experience for students abroad. It not only reminds them of home but can be a form of comfort during times of change; “I missed the food from home. But then I actually started enjoying the food [in Russia]... I missed the food, I missed my family” (Participant #11). Missing the local foods from Zambia was discussed by 6 participants (23%). Specifically, participants missed nshima, which is considered to be the staple food in Zambia. One participant who studied in Russia would bring back mealie meal from Zambia when he visited home during school breaks and would share it with fellow Zambia students. Participants noted the differences of foreign food from the ones they were more familiar with; “We had to adjust to the foods available which were different from what we have in Zambia. For example, where you expect the juice to be sweet it would taste salty” (Participant #20). The desire for more familiar foods such as nshima was a common experience identified within the study.

Subtheme 1.3: Weather. New locations around the world expectedly will have different weather patterns. Weather was mentioned by 7 (27%) of the 26 participants interviewed. Weather was not a major focus during discussion of experiences, it was mentioned in passing by many. Participant #5 stated, “of course climate can also be a challenge somehow but you get used [to it] after a while.” Cold weather was a barrier to acclimating to a new country; cold weather and snow being new to Zambians led to difficulty traveling locally.

Coming from a tropical climate, few Zambians have been introduced to snowy climates. Navigating in this new environment proved a challenge as discussed by 4 (15%) of the participants. Participant #5 stated that, “the weather [in Russia] is cold, that means you need to buy something warm.” Buying new appropriate clothing was necessary to walk between buildings and travel to shops; “The country is very cold but it’s nothing warm clothes cannot solve” (Participant #14). One participant discussed her experience of standing in the snow waiting for a taxi, “it would be winter, it’s snowing and then no one would stop. Like no cab drivers would stop for you, so you would be on the streets for so long” (Participant #3). Learning to navigate and travel in a new climate was an experience shared by many participants.

Subtheme 1.4: Racial Differences. Racism was cited by 17 (65%) participants as one of the challenges experienced during their times studying abroad. Racism and racial discrimination was a prevalent challenge faced by internationally trained medical professionals; “They kept on emphasizing I was a foreigner. That was the only thing, I always felt like a foreigner. No matter what” (Participant #1). The feeling of always being seen as a foreigner and the inability to blend in was noted by participants. The foreign countries participants were studying in did not have a large black population, so dark-skinned individuals from Zambia continued to stand out. Participant #4 discussed her experiences regarding standing out in a non-black community, “you are an African person in an Asian land, so everyone will look at you differently, your hair is different, so everyone will point out like very often the kids would make silly comments but with time I think you get used to it.” Local people would take notice of Zambians because of the unfamiliarity of black skin in their culture. Some locals reacted with interest and curiosity. Participant #10 described her experiences; “not that they were racist, but they were just so excited

to see somebody that was different. I think for me that was quite intriguing ... knowing that people had never seen such a race.”

While some interactions surrounding racial differences were relatively harmless, some individuals reacted in fear resulting in hurtful racism as cited by Participant #2; “There weren’t many foreigners in the city. The locals were never exposed to many foreigners, especially blacks. This made them not want to associate with us or even sit next to us.” Discrimination was cited to have occurred often throughout participants' studies, with even professors and lecturers being discriminatory at times. Participant #10 stated that, “there are some teachers who would actually not maybe grade you the way they would grade a Russian even though you answered almost the same...I think they were always shocked as to why a foreigner would do better than a Russian.” Racial differences were at the core of experiences had by Zambian medical professionals who trained internationally.

Subtheme 1.5: Integration into Zambian Workforce. Although one of the research focuses was experiences of individuals studying internationally, participants brought up many challenges related to returning to Zambia after the completion of their program. For some participants these challenges appeared during the final year of their program when they had the opportunity to go for clinical practice in another country and they chose to complete this year in Zambia. “The divide-foreign vs Zambian trained- still exists several years after completion of studies” (Participant #14). A gap existed between foreign-trained medical professionals and Zambian-trained medical professionals. This divide was identified in the experiences of many participants; “there were situations where foreign trained were treated differently from locally trained medical officers” (Participant #14). These experiences included bullying from peers and other medical professionals in the clinical setting, lacking certain skills required for Zambian

trained medical professionals, and difficulty in finding employment related to education bias towards foreign-trained individuals.

Bullying and discrimination from peers and superiors was an unfortunate experience of many of the participants when they returned to Zambia to practice; “I was thought of as being dull, too slow and faced a lot of bullying” (Participant #20). The medical programs, in the various foreign countries, participants attended had differences in the skill sets that were taught to students. These programs did not train doctors to master more simple procedures such as, “manually checking vital signs, vein puncture and so many procedures that we were not exposed to during the training” (Participant #20). With the gap of knowledge for such skills, those who trained locally and other medical professionals had preconceived ideas about the intelligence of those who were foreign-trained. “The medical personnel already have the notion that foreign trained [people] don’t learn much. So they have the stereotype so loud, that even before you try, you are already dismissed” (Participant #11). Participants described being belittled, called names, and their intelligence put into question.

Because of the differences in the educational programs, participants noted that they were lacking skills required for Zambian practice. “When you come back, there [were] certain skills you were going to be lacking...I was aware that I was going to be lacking certain skills but when I came back, before I joined the workforce I did a few rotations” (Participant #8). The knowledge of tropical diseases and diseases more prevalent to Zambia was also noted as a gap in knowledge by participants. Participant #10 stated, “It was also a challenge and I came back and I saw [that] these are diseases that we focus on in Zambia.” Participant #15 recalled an instance of this, “for example, during one of the doctor’s rounds, my senior shouted at me for not knowing what HIV is and how to manage patients with HIV.” Participant #4 states, “I faced a lot of challenges

especially when it comes to doing some procedures that in China were done by nurses then over here [in Zambia] the doctors do it. So I found those challenges because I wasn't able to do those procedures that my colleagues who were trained here were capable of doing." This knowledge gap continued to fuel the bullying and discrimination directed towards the foreign-trained participants.

Difficulty finding employment was an experience cited by participants. They expressed

Subtheme 1.1: Foreign Languages. Every participant cited language barriers as a challenge faced when studying abroad to varying degrees of difficulty. All but one of the participants studied in countries that had native or national languages other than English. For the participant who studied in the United Kingdom, he was still met with challenges in communications related to native accents despite the UK being an English speaking nation.

That priority is given to Zambian trained professionals first before hiring foreign-trained professionals; "Employment opportunities were first given to Zambian trained medical officers" (Participant #20). When it came to finding employment, foreign trained medical professionals felt left out as, "employment opportunities were first given to Zambian trained medical officers" as cited by Participant #20. Other participants remained unemployed for a period of time; "There are people who stayed in Zambia, without working for years and years, not working, always left out" (Participant #24). Participant #14 expressed their frustration in the Zambian system, "For those who have studied abroad, the authorities should make it easier for them to be incorporated in the system, as in make it easier for them to register and join the practice." The challenges and experiences surrounding returning to Zambia for work were a prevalent theme found throughout the participant interviews.

Theme 2: Factors Associated with Challenges

Objective 1 of the research explored the experiences of the participants and by doing so participants identified various challenges faced. From these challenges, researchers identified the factors that were associated with each. These factors are the circumstances, facts, or influences that contributed to the challenges identified. Within the theme of factors associated with challenges five subthemes emerged. These factors identified in the subthemes include differences in Zambian and foreign curricula, financial restriction, inadequate pre-travel knowledge, university location, and inability to learn foreign language prior to traveling abroad.

Subtheme 2.1: Differences in Zambian and Foreign Curricula. One experience discussed by participants was returning to Zambia and integrating into the Zambian workforce. This challenge arose from the differences in the Zambian approach to education and the approach of the foreign country they studied in. As stated by Participant #5, “the curriculum again is different from what we have here in Zambia.” “The approach to medicine is totally different” (Participant #15). The differences highlighted by participants was a major factor contributing to the challenge of integrating into medical practice in Zambia.

Participants expressed that the foreign country they chose to study in had a more advanced education system than Zambia. This was a factor contributing to the challenges faced as, “it becomes difficult to find students to study abroad because the level [of] education at grade 12 is not [as] advanced as [in Russia]... you find that you have challenges because the first year of learning, it’s like you are learning the basics” (Participant #24). Participants highlighted that they felt unprepared to start at the level in which locals were starting as the standard of education in Zambian secondary schools was behind. Participant #24 further discussed that they valued their education in Russia as they received, “better learning because I feel the education [in Russia] is

way [more] advanced... our education system is quite lagging. It needs some improvement... people struggle because it's more advanced, we were way, way behind." Participants noted that they had to work harder than their peers to catch up and be successful in their studies.

The examination style used in foreign countries was noted as being significantly different than those in Zambia. The differences of education and examinations were often only revealed to participants when they returned to Zambia to take the Zambian licensure exams. "The studying was a bit different in that in China most of the exams were prepared in a specific way... I have noticed that the exam set in Zambia was totally different" (Participant #4). Participant #2 states, "The licensure exams were equally a challenge. What was in the exam is not what we learned in China. I had to start coaching classes just to prepare for the exams focusing on [the] Zambian syllabus." The factors highlighted by the participants contributed to delayed integration into medical practice in Zambia.

More advanced technology was used within medical training and medical facilities in the foreign countries participants studied in. Another factor the participants pointed out was the unavailability of advanced medical equipment within Zambia. During their studies, participants were exposed to advanced medical equipment which was not available for practice after returning to Zambia; "they have modern equipment in the UK compared to Zambia. So after taking time studying in the UK even after this time the government has not purchased the equipment for calibration and testing of biosafety cabinets, so it's quite difficult to continue with practice where there is no equipment" (Participant # 5). According to Participant # 4 "The technology there is more advanced and you're a bit more up-to-date, there are certain procedures or methods that they use that we [are] not able to use yet here, because we are still a developing country. But having

that exposure, because at the end of the day you come back and it will help you develop your country.”

Along with more advanced technology, more up-to-date medical practices and procedures were noted by participants. As expressed by participant #23, “the top research and ongoing programs are, like, the latest information in terms of medicine development.” There was a desire to take the knowledge of medical advancements back to Zambia to improve patient treatment and care; “there are so many things that you can say, like I think this could be introduced in Zambia or I think [that] we could do better because the Russians do it like this.” “You know the standards you’re supposed to achieve, so even when you’re here, you know what you’re aiming for. Whereas if you’re [in Zambia], you never really know that there’s more. You wouldn’t realize that there’s a lack” (Participant #23). The knowledge of both developed countries' medical standards compared with those of Zambia gave participants the aspiration to apply those practices when they returned to the workforce in Zambia.

Diseases focused on in foreign nations were regionally specific which led to less knowledge of prevalent diseases in Zambia. Participant #10 states that, “even the education that we received is totally different because there you are actually taught about the diseases that are in that country and how they do their things rather than teaching you the broad medicine.” This knowledge gap contributed to the challenge of integrating into the Zambian workforce. On the advice of a peer, Participant #15 was aware that this factor contributed to the challenges experienced; “He advised me to frequently come to Zambia for clinical practice which I started doing frequently and I spent 2 months in Zambian hospitals just to catch up with clinical experience.” The factor of differences in Zambian and foreign education contributed to challenges faced by participants.

Subtheme 2.2: Financial Restrictions. While 15 (58%) of the participants indicated that they had no financial challenges while studying abroad, some participants were faced with some challenges including delayed remission of funds by the bursaries committee, fluctuations in the exchange rates, and using a weaker currency against strong currencies in foreign countries. Financial restrictions were factors that led to challenges such as graduation delays and pressure on the student and family to earn school fees or to maintain scholarships. One factor that led to further challenges was due to the exchange rate of the *Zambian* currency.

Scholarships are one way that many students are able to study internationally. Many students rely on outside funds to be able to pursue education. Despite having scholarships, financial restrictions still contributed to the challenges faced by participants. “Towards the end of my studies I was forgotten. The bursaries committee had forgotten about me. They delayed sending money and never purchased my return ticket on time. I remained in Cuba for another 2 months after completing my studies. There were no means of sending money by any family member at that time” (Participant #13). For those students who were on “self-pay” finances were also of concern. One participant was unable to rely on scholarship, “at that time there was no *Ukrainian* scholarships for *Zambians*” (Participant #14). This led to pressure on the student and his family to earn the money for school fees. Financial restrictions led to delays in graduation and obtaining a diploma for one participant; “I was not allowed to graduate because of outstanding fees” (Participant #17). Financial restrictions were a prevalent factor that led to challenges by students both on self-pay and those on scholarship.

The *Zambia* kwacha is considered a weaker currency and will not go as far as *US* dollars (*USD*) or stronger currencies. Participant #5 stated, “It becomes very difficult especially for us in *Zambia*, it means you have to save for quite some time or even get a loan.” With a fluctuating

currency, the exchange rate would impact students' ability to have financial stability whilst abroad; "Visa clearance and financial challenges because when you convert the kwacha it's not matching with the money [in the UK]" (Participant #5). Even with what would be considered a lot of money in Zambia, because of exchange rates those finances did not last as long in a foreign country, "for example when you have a K15000 from here and you are going to the UK, when you convert it you will find that the money can only buy about 4 meals, so sometimes it's so frustrating" (Participant #5). Issues of inflation related to the COVID-19 pandemic even impacted some participants. "I faced some financial challenges, especially during COVID time, because there was the inflation and the kwacha to the dollar was high, so during that time it was quiet hard because now the fees had gone up and things were expensive because of the same inflation, accommodation and all that" (Participant #4). Participant #9 stated, "Studying abroad is expensive especially when the kwacha has lost value and when you are from underprivileged families." Challenges faced by medical professionals studying abroad were highly impacted by different forms of financial restrictions.

Subtheme 2.3: Inadequate Pre-Travel Knowledge. Of the challenges faced by Zambian medical professionals who studied internationally there were many challenges that arose when returning to Zambia to join the workforce. A major factor influencing this challenge is related to the knowledge they had prior to embarking on studying internationally. "Upon returning to Zambia, there were no clear instructions on what to do next. It was challenging because there was no one to guide us on the next steps" (Participant #13). The procedures on how to progress once completing an international program were not clearly specified to participants and contributed to the challenges they faced. "If you were foreign trained you would have to come back... they need to check if your school is accredited and you need to write the HPCZ licensing board in Zambia.

Which by then, I think local students did not do. So that was kind of a lot of stuff I didn't expect before I went to university" (Participant #3). Procedures and examinations were required once foreign-trained students returned to Zambia which was not previously communicated to them. This lack of knowledge prior to starting their program of study was a factor in the challenges they face when returning to Zambia.

Lack of research into the program of study, the selected institution of learning, and expectations upon returning to Zambia after completion of studies was another factor cited to have contributed to the challenges faced by the participants. The participants emphasized, "I would tell them that they should do a lot of research into the university they are going to, because there are so many universities out there" (Participant #4). When discussing whether other prospective students should pursue international studies, participants generally recommended that thorough research should be done prior to making any decisions, "if they know what they are getting into. I think that when I went there I didn't know about coming back to do exams and me having to do rotations again at local hospitals ... So if they're aware of all the steps that they have to do when they get back, then sure enough, I recommend it" (Participant #3).

Subtheme 2.4: University Location. Six (8%) participants reported facing racist discrimination while studying abroad. The affected participants related this experience to the location of the university. One participant discussed that studying at a university located in a small town where the locals were not exposed to a lot of Africans compounded these challenges of racism. "I think they weren't just exposed to a lot of Africans... that was the reason why we faced such kinds of discrimination. My city was a very small city and it was full of old people so they've never really gotten to see this part of the other culture" (Participant #10). The realization that many

locals lacked exposure to different races and led to racial discrimination. Participant #3 stated, “You start to realize that there’s parts of China where they’re just not exposed to black people.”

Another participant narrated that their group of study was the second group of Africans studying in that town. Hence, the locals were not comfortable with dark skinned people. “Because the town I was studying in, Mainchung, we were, I believe, the second batch of Africans to be there. So for a lot of them it was just them not being very comfortable with seeing dark skinned people.” (Participant # 23). The location of the university was identified within smaller towns where less foreigners usually travel to; “because my city was a small city – it was not a big city like these cities like Moscow, Petersburg – these are tourist capitals where you know people are exposed to a wide range of people” (Participant #10). Participant #11 also cited the smaller towns as a factor contributing to issues of racism, “I felt that the racism was so much because I wasn’t in a city. So my school was like the first black, or international school. So there were some old people who had never met a black person in their entire life.” University location was a factor identified that added to the challenges of racial discrimination while studying foreign countries.

Subtheme 2.5: Inability to Learn Foreign Language Prior to Travel Abroad. Three (12%) participants expressed their desire to have been able to start learning the language prior to traveling abroad. One participant discussed how his program typically required language courses prior to travel, but because of a delay in admission to the program, he was not able to take these pre-travel language classes which caused him to be disadvantaged. “I never had the opportunity to learn the language prior to departure” (Participant #15). From the time of being accepted into a foreign program to the point where students are actually moving abroad is limited, so the opportunity to study the language was not available to them.

Theme 3: Measures Implemented to Overcome Challenges

Participants reacted differently and took different actions in order to overcome the different challenges they faced during training and after returning back to Zambia. From their different expressions, the following themes emerged.

Subtheme 3.1: Encouragement and self-motivation. Encouragement and self-motivation was presented as one of the factors that drove some participants to never give up. This was displayed in the form of threats from family members' while others due to pressure of an uneasy environment by failing to interact due to language barrier so they had to work hard to the best of their abilities so as to later become comfortable. For example Participant #1 explained that, "you know I received consistent reminders from people back home, saying 'you know how much you're paying right?' So that was the pull as well. And also just to practice what you came there for, other than that, I would have lived there for a long time." Others found the joy and excitement of having new experiences as the motivation they needed to persist; "the excitement helped me to settle in within 6 months and I was eager to learn. I had prepared myself psychologically and was ready to overcome whatever challenges" (Participant #2). Participants were able to draw on motivation from both internal and external sources in order to complete their studies. Others explained that learning a language was key in adapting for example; Participant #1 noted that, "it was aggressive, I didn't want to feel the way I was feeling. So I was very aggressive, I put myself out there. It was six months, I was learning the languages and then after that I was very comfortable."

When asked about how they overcame the challenges they faced while they came back to Zambia, participants gave notable responses such as; "I needed to relearn everything from the start like manually checking vital signs, vein puncture and so many procedures that we were not exposed to during the training" (Participant #20). Participants were aware of the increased effort

they would need to exert in order to be successful, especially when compared to their Zambian-trained peers; “In terms of settling back into Zambia, I had to put in extra work. Whatever my Zambian trained colleagues were doing, my effort was twice as much” (Participant #13). Others added that, “just being aware that when you come back, there were certain skills you were going to be lacking. That was very helpful, because I knew I wouldn’t go straight into working when I came back” (Participant #8).

When participants discussed the language barriers they face while abroad, the motivation of the individual was the sub theme that emerged. Of the 26 participants, 6 (23%) expressed the sentiment that they were motivated to embrace the new language. Personality type and excitement to learn a foreign language was what participants cited as the reason they were able to push forward in order to complete their studies. Participant #15 discussed that, “when I learned the language, it made it easier to interact with the locals which promoted further understanding of the language.”

In order to complete their studies successfully learning the new language was a requirement. The necessity of understanding the local language was the driving factor that pushed individuals to learn; “with us, the university, it’s like a language is [required]. If you don’t pass that you don’t go into second year. So that was also one of the reasons I had to learn Chinese as much as possible” (Participant #1). For some individuals the program of study was in the foreign language and became a requirement for success; “I took Chinese for a year, but I also had lectures in Chinese. My program was taught in Chinese. Unfortunately the program, because I was on scholarship, was in Chinese” (Participant #25). “Spanish is used in Cuba, I had to learn Spanish in the first years of training and continued learning throughout my training” (Participant #13). Because of the requirements to learn the new language, participants cited this as the motivating factor in learning. Others added that; “By learning the language, I feel like that’s what sorted out

most of the issues. Then, I think when it comes to, it also kind of requires the Chinese people there to, like, get comfortable with you” (Participant 23). “Integrating with Chinese people is easier once you learn the language. Once they realize you can speak to them, they are much more friendly and welcoming and actually want to converse with foreigners” (Participant 26). “I am a Christian, I am a firm believer of Christ, and so I would pray more, study more, we created friends fortunately from all those universities so it was easy to mingle at a certain time” (Participant #20).

Subtheme 3.2: Friends and Family Support. Participants cited building a family and community around them as one of the ways they were able to overcome challenges. Friends and family support was one of the themes that emerged. Some participants had family members in the host country where they studied who supported them emotionally and financially, while others made friends from the host nation and among themselves as foreigners so as to encourage each other in order to overcome the challenges while in the host nation. Notable are the responses below:

“I had support from my family overseas. They helped me somehow and I had friends that came through and I also saved some money, but I had got a loan” (Participant #4).

“The goodness is that I was not alone, I had friends and we all were a lot of foreigners from different countries. So we all pushed ourselves to learn the language and to know why we came there” (Participant #10).

“I had to join a community of foreign trained practitioners and that way, we supported each other through the adaptation process, shared notes on how to overcome the challenges we were facing” (Participant #13).

“I formed a lot of friends from Asians who helped me with communication and understanding the language” (Participant #22).

“I found a new family in foreigners, so that’s what really kept me going, the family I found there. The friends I made, the family I had, so after some time it became better” (Participant #25).

Subtheme 3.3: Mentorship and Support. Is one of the ways that helped participants in overcoming the challenges like adapting and learning a language in the host countries, certain institutions had put up such deliberate measures so as to help foreign students to learn the language and adapt to the culture in the host nations; these were noted in their narrations below:

“The institution was helpful when it came to orientation and helping us settle, we were assigned a mentor who we could call in case we needed anything. That was helpful” (Participant #2).

“There’s a program that we had where you would be either assigned a Chinese family or, like, you’d have interactions with Chinese students, so you could get to know each other and get integrated into their culture. So that helped us overcome that” (Participant #24).

Subtheme 3.4. Avoidance Coping. One of the ways of coping that emerged from the participants was avoidance. This was in relation to overcoming racism and segregation. After being subjected to racism in the host nations. Participants overcame these challenges by avoidance as noted from their responses:

“I think avoiding certain areas which had a lot of racism. Something I just did, pretty much I just stopped going to certain areas” (Participant #3).

“I just refused that’s all, when I wasn’t comfortable with someone touching my hair or taking pictures” (Participant #6).

“You just have to have a mentality of understanding, honestly. If you take it at heart it will get to you and then life will become very difficult. So something you just overlook and life goes on. If you really take it to heart, life becomes difficult for you” (Participant #24).

DISCUSSION

Theme 1: Experiences

Zambian students still face the challenges discussed within the literature review such as language barriers, cultural differences, dietary preferences, but unique challenges arose, such as integrating back into Zambian work culture where individuals found themselves experiencing bullying by peers, delays in finding employment, a gap in knowledge in some medical procedures, and a less organized working environment in Zambia when compared to how they were taught in the programs abroad. Zambian medical professionals who trained internationally have experiences that are unique to them. These experiences were events or occurrences that left impressions on the participants. Participants were asked to recall experiences from different stages of their time abroad. The themes that emerged from participants' responses ranged from positive experiences to challenges that they encountered. The majority of participants cited that the time they spent abroad was invaluable to them as it helped broaden their perspective of the world, they gained new knowledge and skills, and that it shaped the person they are today. Despite the overall experience being viewed as positive, participants repeatedly cited the challenges as some of the most memorable experiences they had.

Experiences that discussed challenges that were highlighted by the participants included language barriers, diet, weather, racial differences and issues surrounding returning to Zambia to integrate into the workforce. Challenges such as cultural differences, language barriers, academic requirements, financial difficulties, homesickness, or physical and mental health issues have been cited in previous studies and are well understood within the existing literature (Bakloshova & Kasakov, 2016; Heiberg et al., 2019). Despite an understanding of some of these challenges did not diminish their significance to participants. Two particular experiences brought forward by

participants appeared to be more unique to Zambian students; racial differences and integration into the Zambian workforce.

Culture and culture shock can play a role in adding to the mental stress international students' face whilst studying abroad (Khanal & Gaulee, 2019). Through the thematic analysis it became increasingly clear that Zambians, as black people of color, face racial discrimination and racism in foreign countries. Eighteen (69%) participants studied in China, 5 (19%) studied in Russian, 1 (3.8%) studied in Ukraine, 1 (3.8%) studied in the United Kingdom, and 1 (3.8%) studied in Cuba. The predominant race in these countries include white East Slavic, white European, and Chinese. The only country with mixed cultural populations with African origins was Cuba. With 7 (27%) of the participants having studied in predominantly white countries and 18 (69%) studying in China with a predominantly Chinese population, their foreign heritage was visible as evident by their darker skin. Preconceptions and stereotypes can pose challenges to students coming from culturally different backgrounds than their host country (Sobkowiak, 2019). Participants cited experiences of blatant racism related to the color of their skin. Locals would choose not to associate with them leading to issues with transportation, forming friendships, and gaining experience within their clinical practice. Participants often felt that lack of exposure to different races was the factor that led to the challenges they faced surrounding racism. One participant even discussed being discriminated against in the classroom setting by the professor. Although participants did feel hurt by the racism they experienced, most felt they were able to ignore the interactions and persist in their studies.

Integration into the Zambian workforce was an experience that was discussed by 17 (65%) of the participants. There is fragmented literature surrounding international students' workforce integration surrounding multiple disciplines such as management, education, and sociology (Han

et al., 2022). The focus of studies regarding international students primarily “has been on their academic, sociocultural, and psychological adjustment while completing their education” (Han et al., 2022). There is insufficient research surrounding post-graduation employment and the integration of international students into the workforce of receiving countries. As evident by the experiences of the participants, returning to Zambia and attempting to join the Zambian medical workforce was a significant challenge faced. The process to obtain a license after completing an international program was not clear in Zambia. Zambian licensure exams were structured differently than those within the programs completed internationally. Participants cited bullying from peers and superiors because of their foreign training. Participants also noted discrimination in that employers would blatantly choose Zambian trained professionals before considering a foreign trained person. These various challenges compound the need for further research and understanding of integration into the Zambian workforce post international studies.

Theme 2: Factors Associated with Challenges

Incorporating internationally trained health professionals in the Zambian workforce plays a role in addressing shortages in human resources for health in the country. While integrating a labor force that has been exposed to advanced education systems strengthens research, evidence-based practice and contributes significantly to a global wealth of experience, it comes at a cost for those professionals who train internationally. The research findings identified various factors associated with the challenges faced by internationally trained health professionals while studying abroad and upon completion of their programs of study. The influencers of the identified challenges include differences in the Zambian curriculum compared to curricula in various universities attended by the study participants, differences in Zambian educational models and

foreign models, financial restrictions, inadequate pre-departure knowledge, university location as well as inability to learn the foreign language prior to traveling abroad. A study on internationalization of the curriculum in health programs by Davey (2023), addresses the multicultural health related environments that health professionals are likely to practice from as well as encountering global health challenges. The author further states the need for universities and other institutions of higher learning to develop strategies that will enable graduating students to practice competently in a global environment. The differences that exist in the curricula create a barrier for internationally trained health professionals as it requires them to readjust after completion of studies and re-learn medical practice in their home country. Addressing the differences through government policies and regulators of health professional training by internationalizing the curricula would improve professional practice and address global health challenges.

Another factor that the internationally trained health professionals encountered was financial restrictions that may have been related to additional unforeseen expenses that were not covered by scholarships and some hidden costs that were not reflected in the program fee structure. Participants associated the financial restrictions with fluctuations in foreign exchange rates, instability of the Zambian currency and inefficiency in financial aids for those under government sponsorship. Financial restrictions have been identified as one of the factors causing stress and anxiety in foreign trained professionals. This factor has been associated with destabilization of student academic activities and brings about an interruption in academic performance (Larbi et al., 2022). Although the majority of the participants reported minimal financial challenges while studying abroad, it is important to adequately address issues surrounding funding of study programs pursued internationally.

Inadequate pre-travel knowledge, the location of the university and inability to learn foreign language prior to travel all center on inadequate pre-departure preparation. Pre-departure preparation enables candidates wishing to study abroad identify goals, expectations and explore the cultural differences they are likely to face (Chan et al., 2018). The lack of thorough investigation into the location of the university, the lack of information on expectations after completion of studies and failure to learn the language prior to travel contributed to challenges faced by internationally trained professionals while in the host country and returning to their home country after completion of studies.

Theme 3: Measures Implemented to Overcome Challenges

The study findings showed that participants utilized measures like avoidance coping, friends and family support, mentorship and support and encouragement and self-motivation in order to overcome the challenges they faced. Particularly, participants reacted differently to challenges and took different actions for different challenges, for example avoidance coping was used mostly to overcome racism, while encouragement and self-motivation was commonly used for academic challenges and learning of the new language while mentorship and Support programs which were organized by certain institutions was to help participants learn the language and culture by assigning them a mentor or the family. These findings correspond with the study finding of Sobkowiak, (2019) who postulated that despite stressors caused by cultural differences, many students were prompted to develop better coping strategies allowing them to foster intercultural competences. On the contrary, even though certain strategies like avoidance coping were utilized, it involves cognitive and behavioral efforts oriented toward denying, minimizing, or otherwise avoiding dealing directly with stressful demands, therefore, it is closely linked to distress and

depression (Holahan et al., 2005). However, the use of avoidance coping among the foreign-trained can be attributed to failure to communicate and express themselves. This is evident in by participants having difficulties denying unpleasant things politely, such as being touched and taking pictures of them in public places without permission.

CONCLUSION

The theme of experiences clearly identified as participants reflected on various experiences that stood out from their time abroad. Many of the subthemes identified overlapped with common challenges that many international students face such as diet, weather, and language barriers. Although each of these subthemes were important experiences of the participants, more unique experiences revealed themselves. These experiences included challenges that stemmed from racial differences and integration into the Zambian workforce. Exploring these challenges and experiences led to the emphasis on the need for further research and exploration into these aspects of international experiences.

The theme of factors associated with challenges identified different factors that were led to or influenced the challenges faced by international trained Zambians. The influencers of the identified challenges include differences in the Zambian curriculum compared to curricula in various universities attended by the study participants, differences in Zambian educational models and foreign models, financial restrictions, inadequate pre-departure knowledge, university location as well as inability to learn the foreign language prior to traveling abroad. The differences that exist in the curricula create a barrier for internationally trained health professionals as it requires them to readjust after completion of studies and re-learn medical practice in their home country. Understanding this as a factor of challenges can be used to shape employment policy in home

countries and curricula policy by foreign institutions. The financial restrictions related to currency exchange can push foreign institutions to standardize billing into a stable currency. Though this will not eliminate all financial restrictions, it will help to mitigate financially based challenges.

The study findings showed that participants utilized measures like avoidance coping, friends and family support, mentorship and support and encouragement and self-motivation in order to overcome the challenges they faced. Participants cited implementing these measures to help overcome challenges they faced. By identifying coping strategies, further investigation into the effectiveness of each will help to better prepare prospective students who are interested in pursuing international studies.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Some of the challenges identified within the literature review were not expressed to be the most difficult issues faced by Zambian medical professionals. Many participants expressed that though language, food, and weather were somewhat of a challenge; the integration into the Zambian workforce challenges they faced were far more significant to them. Researchers recommend further investigations into this area of international educational experiences. Other areas of further research are in the effectiveness of various coping strategies and techniques used by participants to overcome challenges.

Recommendations to the Zambian scholarship programs have also been made as a result of the findings. Scholarship programs should require language programs prior to travel, explain the process of when they complete their studies and return to Zambia.

Recommendations for governing bodies include; The Ministry of Health (MoH) and the Ministry of Education (MoE). Researchers recommend that MoE should ensure that when students

are going abroad they should be fully supported with financial assistance, if possible financial assistance be in USD to mitigate effects of kwacha depreciation. The Ministry of Health should design and implement a program for foreign-trained health personnel to be integrated into the Zambian workforce more seamlessly. Educating Zambian-trained staff on how to conduct themselves with professional behavior will help to mitigate the bullying and discrimination that occurs.

REFERENCES

- Baklashova, T. A. & Kazakov, A. V. (2016). Challenges of international students' adjustment to a higher education institution. *Journal of Environmental & Science Education, 11*(8). 10.12973/ijese.2016.557a
- Chan, E. A., Liu, J. Y. W., Fung, K. H. K., Tsang, P.L., Yuen J. (2018). Pre-departure preparation and co-curricular activities for Students' intercultural exchange: A mixed-methods study. *Nurse Educ Today, 2018*(63), 43-49. 10.1016/j.nedt.2018.01.020.
- Creswell, J. W., & Creswell, D. J. (2018). *Research design: Qualitative and mixed methods approaches* (5th Ed.). Sage Publications, Inc.
- Davey A. K. (2023). Internationalization of the curriculum in health programs. *BMC medical education, 23*(1), 285. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12909-023-04271-8>
- Han, Y., Gulanowski, D., & Sears, G. J. (2022). International student graduates' workforce integration: A systematic review. *International Journal of Intercultural Relations, 86*, 163–189. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijintrel.2021.11.003>.
- Heiberg, I. G., Dahl, H., & Eriksen, K. A. (2019). How can studying abroad nurture nursing students' intellectual experience? *Nurse Education in Practice, 41*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nepr.2019.102644>
- Holahan, C. J., Moos, R. H., Holahan, C. K., Brennan, P. L., & Schutte, K. K. (2005). Stress generation, avoidance coping, and depressive symptoms: A 10-year model. *Journal of Consulting and Clinical Psychology, 73*(4), 658–666. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-006X.73.4.658>

- Khanal, J., & Gaulee, U. (2019). Challenges of international students from pre-departure to post-study: A literature review. *Journal of International Students*, 9(2).
<https://doi.org/10.32674/jis.v9i2.673>
- Larbi, F. O., Ma, Z., Fang, Z., Virlanuta, F. O., Bărbuță-Mișu, N., and Deniz, G. (2022). Financial anxiety among international students in higher education: A comparative analysis between international students in the United States of America and China" *Sustainability*, 14(7). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14073743>
- Sobkowiak, P. (2019). The impact of studying abroad on students' intercultural competence: An interview study. *Studies in Second Language Learning and Teaching*, 9(4), 681–710. <https://doi.org/10.14746/ssllt.2019.9.4.6>